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Important Aspects of Preparing Students of Pre-School Education for Cooperation with Parents through Pedagogical Practice

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***Abstract:** In this article discussion about important aspects of preparing students of pre-school education for cooperation with parents through pedagogical practice.*

***Key words:** pre-school, education, pedagogical practice, aspects, higher education, considered, meet, requirement.*

Introduction. The future of every country depends on the field of education, which means that it is necessary to form students of higher education who meet the requirements of not only today, but also tomorrow. In particular, preschool education is considered one of the leading factors of training a future educator by means of pedagogical practice in the case of students.

It is known that pedagogical practice is one of the important stages of preparing students for the profession. Pedagogical activity and the formation of readiness for its activation are carried out only in conditions as close as possible to the interaction of theoretical and knowledge and the real conditions of future professional activity. It helps not only to form professional skills, but also to form professionally important qualities.

Discussion. An important role is played by students in cooperation with the family, especially parents, through the means of pedagogical practice. This will help students to improve their professional activities.

It is appropriate to rely on the following factors when preparing students to work in cooperation with parents:

- Observation and diagnostic analysis of the peculiarities of the pupils themselves and their age;
- To study the social status of the parents of the group of students assigned to the student during the pedagogical practice;

- Collecting information for parents about their children's positive qualities acquired over a certain period of time;
- Planning and organizing sincere conversations with parents and questionnaires;

In the future, it is necessary to pay attention to the content of the work carried out by the educators of the preschool educational organization with the family in order to develop students into mature specialists. Practicing students in this:

- the content of the work carried out in the preschool education organization on child education, family strengthening, motherhood and childhood protection;
- to parents that they are responsible for the education of their children before the state and society;
- informing parents about the knowledge and skills necessary for raising children (acquainting them with the age, anatomical-physiological and mental characteristics of children, the content, methods and conditions of raising them in the family);
- cooperation with the family in raising a child, monitoring the proper upbringing of a child, studying and popularizing the best examples of family upbringing[1].

It is known that positive results can be achieved if the best qualities acquired by the child in MTT are continued in the family environment, and the best qualities acquired in the family are used in MTT.

Students should not only see the positive things in their experience of family upbringing, but also support it, and on the basis of this, parents should pay attention to the tasks that have not yet been resolved in child upbringing.

In planning, organizing and leading the above works, a practical leader attached from higher education and an educator attached from MTT are responsible.

He should take an active part in general and group meetings, open-door days for parents, talks and consultations, organization of exhibitions and concerts in parenting organizations [2].

A lot of work with parents is carried out by the educator - pedagogue, because he sees the changes taking place in the upbringing of the child more than anyone else and gets to know the children's life closely. He gives recommendations to parents on what to pay more attention to in raising children, preparing them for school education, maintaining health, properly organizing food and daily routine, etc.[3] In these processes, the direct participation of the practicing student is important.

During the internship, students will acquire the following skills and qualifications:

- to be able to organize one's pedagogical activity and apply it in practice;
- to have communication skills in cooperation with parents;
- creatively finding solutions to various pedagogical problems that arise;
- the ability to organize various types of educational activities that are more effective in learning relevant topics and programs;
- implements important competencies such as acquisition of professional and personal qualities within the framework of cooperation [4].

Conclusion. In a word, students get acquainted with highly qualified specialists and analyze the professional environment. Pedagogical practice focuses students' attention on professional and

personal development, activation of personal resources and formation of professional position to solve their internal problems.

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